

Surgical Scene Understanding using Context Prompting for Multimodal Large Language Models

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Abstract. Surgical video analysis requires domain-specific expertise and knowledge extraction. Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches for surgical video analysis rely on extensive computational resources, large annotated datasets, and specialised architectures while offering limited explainability. This work explores the potential of Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) for surgical video analysis. Specifically, we develop an interactive framework to use the Gemini API to identify instrument-verb-target triplets in laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos. Our approach implements a dual-context prompt engineering approach that comprises a surgical context prompt (SCP) and a surgical analysis prompt (SAP) that separates domain context knowledge from the analytical task. The dual-context prompts utilised XML-structured knowledge representation with distinct SCP and SAP. Evaluation on the validation set of CholecT50 (laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos) dataset demonstrates the potential of MLLM to analyze surgical frames and identify the instrument-verb-target triplets. However, the accuracy measure is lower than that of purpose-built models. This work establishes a valuable foundation for MLLM applications in surgical education and research, with potential to evolve and improve with our ongoing work in this direction. **150–250 words.**

Keywords: Multimodal · LLMs · prompt engineering · surgery.

1 Introduction

Surgical video recordings are rich in information and provide valuable information for surgical skills assessment, training, and education. However, traditional domain-specific AI models for knowledge extraction are time-consuming and resource-hungry [1], [2]. Manual review methods and human assessments are also prone to human bias, inter-reviewer variability [6]. The complicated interplay between anatomical features, surgical tools, and surgeon activities presents a multifaceted challenge that requires advanced computational techniques [2].

Recent AI-based models for analyzing complex interactions in surgical videos rely on significant computational resources, time for training, and inferences

[3]. Furthermore, building domain-specific AI models demands large annotated data, which is particularly challenging for smaller clinics and research groups to obtain due to privacy concerns and the specialized expertise required. Finally, generalization of purpose-built surgical video analysis models is still limited to specific procedures only [4], [5].

Recent developments in multimodal large language models (LLMs) have opened new opportunities in surgical video analysis. There is a rising interest in exploring multimodal LLMs for surgical video analysis for applications such as identifying anatomy, recognizing surgical tools, and classifying the surgical procedure, thus navigating the complex landscape of surgical scene analysis [4]. However, such developments on multimodal generative AI and LLMs for medical video data including surgical video data are in very early stages [7], [8]. This study explores the potential of MLLMs to interpret surgical scenes in laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos. More specifically, it demonstrates the capability of Gemini (*the Gemini-Flash-2.0 model*) to recognize the instruments, the target tissues, and the surgical action in a given surgical frame, building on the triplet recognition concept introduced by Nwoye et al [1], [5]. Furthermore, it presents an interactive web demo interface where users can upload surgical images for analysis, providing both qualitative and quantitative analysis and demonstrating the system’s capabilities to medical professionals and the general audience. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to explore the potential of Gemini for surgical video analysis in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

2 Methodology

Dataset: We utilize the CholecT50 dataset that contains 50 endoscopic videos (laparoscopic cholecystectomy videos) from the University Hospital Strasbourg, France. The de-identified dataset comes with rich annotations and provides labels for the triplets (instrument, verb, target), phases of the various stages of the surgical procedure. In addition, five videos also contain spatial bounding boxes for instrument localization.

Pipeline: We introduce a dual-context prompt engineering approach that separates domain knowledge from analytical instructions. The modular prompt implementation separates the theoretical and practical understanding tasks and helps create a more flexible and efficient analytical framework. Our approach sends two sequential prompts to the Gemini API. First, the surgical context prompt (SCP) provides a context to help develop domain knowledge about laparoscopic cholecystectomy, detailing instrument visual characteristics and discriminative features, action patterns, and their visual manifestations. The SCP provides foundational knowledge on the surgical context. The second prompt is the surgical analysis prompt (SAP), which provides specific instructions on the analytical approach and details of the structured output. The SAP helps prevent common misidentification and ensures a consistent structural output format. The SCP allows context catching, i.e., the context is required once and cached for subsequent frame analysis, thus helping reduce token consumption. The modular

Fig. 1. High-level representation of the dual-context prompt engineering architecture.

implementation of the dual-context prompt also allowed modification of either prompts and analysis of the generated output for optimisation. Figure 1 shows a high-level representation of the dual-context prompt architecture.

3 Initial results

The evaluation was conducted on two distinct subsets from the CholecT50 dataset. The first test set had 5 videos randomly chosen from the dataset comprising 8,744 frames and 14,348 surgical actions. The second test set was the official test set of the CholecT50 challenge, comprising five videos with 1,128 frames and 1,774 surgical actions. The pipeline performs recognition of the instrument-verb-target triplets in a given laparoscopy frame (or batch of frames), providing a standardized, structured output aligned with the dataset annotation format. It also provides a quantitative assessment in terms of precision-recall values. Finally, it offers an interactive web interface that enables users to upload and analyze surgical frames, providing a side-by-side comparison with expert annotations. While initial accuracy is lower than that of specialized deep learning architectures, the pipeline offers an effective testbed for different prompting techniques in multimodal LLMs for surgical AI. The pipeline was evaluated on both the test sets using the same approaches. Performance in terms of accuracy and macro F1 score is summarized in Table 1. Evaluation on the official test set allowed for contextual comparison of our approach against existing benchmarks.

Demo: We also aim to show an interactive web demo at the conference where users can upload surgical frames to get analyzed by the pipeline (see Figure 2).

Table 1. Summary of results on 5 videos (8,744 frames and 14,348 surgical actions) used as test set.

Component	Average accuracy	Average Macro F1
Instruments	34.36	24.11
Action	9.46	6.36
Target (anatomy)	9.68	5.72

Fig. 2. Screenshots from the interactive web demo showing the features of the pipeline and the output of multimodal LLMs for a given surgical frame.

Initial results on the CholecT50 dataset demonstrate the potential of the pipeline to recognize the instruments, action, and target tissues. Higher success rates are recorded for instrument recognition than for verb and target recognition. Class-specific performance, in terms of F1 score for top-3 instruments, was 60.74-67.59% for grasper, 22.00-39.26% (for hook), and 9.41-26.07% for scissors. Likewise, top performance target tissues were recorded for the gallbladder, 25.92-42.0% for the gallbladder.

Common confusion patterns: Hook instrument was frequently misidentified as bipolar forceps. Retract action was frequently misidentified as gasp, while dissect was often confused with coagulate. The gallbladder was often confused with the cystic plate.

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